

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12606988>
UDC 004.89

INVESTIGATIONS OF DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHMS IN THE PROBLEMS OF CLASSIFICATION, FORECASTING, IMAGES PROCESSING AND RECOGNITION

G.I. Hamidov,

Information Technology Department,
Baku

Annotation: The goal of the work is to investigate and compare the effectiveness of four deep learning optimization algorithms SGD, Adam, Adagrad and RMSprop in forecasting and pattern recognition tasks. The results of the work – in the process of the work, a comparative analysis of deep learning optimization algorithms was carried out. For this, 5 data sets were selected and prepared for model training. Models with different architectures were created according to each data set. Models were compiled and trained. At the compilation stage, the loss function for each model was determined according to the task, as well as the metrics by which the performance of the model will be evaluated. After training the model, the corresponding losses and metrics were measured on the test data. All results were analyzed and conclusions drawn.

Keywords: DL optimization algorithms, efficiency estimation in the problems of regression analysis, images recognition

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ АЛГОРИТМОВ ГЛУБОКОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ЗАДАЧАХ КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ, ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЯ, ОБРАБОТКИ И РАСПОЗНАВАНИЯ ИЗОБРАЖЕНИЙ

Г.И. Гамидов,

Департамент информационных технологий,
г. Баку

Аннотация: Целью работы является исследование и сравнение эффективности четырех алгоритмов оптимизации глубокого обучения SGD, Adam, Adagrad и RMSprop в задачах

прогнозирования и распознавания образов. Результаты работы – в процессе работы был проведен сравнительный анализ алгоритмов оптимизации глубокого обучения. Для этого было выбрано 5 наборов данных и подготовлено для обучения модели. Для каждого набора данных были созданы модели с разной архитектурой. Модели были скомпилированы и обучены. На этапе компиляции определялась функция потерь для каждой модели согласно поставленной задаче, а также метрики, по которым будет оцениваться производительность модели. После обучения модели соответствующие потери и метрики были измерены на тестовых данных. Все результаты были проанализированы и сделаны выводы.

Ключевые слова: алгоритмы оптимизации DL, оценка эффективности в задачах регрессионного анализа, распознавание изображений

KLASSİFİKASIYA, PROQNOZLAŞDIRMA, TƏSVİRLƏRİN EMALI VƏ TANINMASI PROBLEMLƏRİNDƏ DƏRİN TƏLİM ALQORİTMLƏRİNİN TƏDQIQI

Q.İ. Həmidov,

İnformasiya Texnologiyaları Departamenti,
Bakı

Annotasiya: İşin məqsədi SGD, Adam, Adagrad və RMSprop dörd dərin təlim optimallaşdırma alqoritminin proqnozlaşdırma və nümunələrin tanınması problemlərində effektivliyini araşdırmaq və müqayisə etməkdir. İşin nəticələri – iş zamanı dərin təlim optimallaşdırma alqoritmlərinin müqayisəli təhlili aparılmışdır. Bu məqsədlə 5 məlumat dəsti seçilmiş və model təlimi üçün hazırlanmışdır. Hər bir məlumat dəsti üçün müxtəlif arxitekturaya malik modellər yaradılmışdır. Modellər tərtib edilmiş və öyrədilmişdir. Kompilyasiya mərhələsində hər bir model üçün itki funksiyası tapşırığa, eləcə də modelin performansının qiymətləndiriləcəyi metrikalara uyğun olaraq müəyyən edilmişdir. Modeli öyrətdikdən sonra sınaq məlumatlarında müvafiq itkilər və ölçülər ölçülmüşdür. Bütün nəticələr təhlil edilmiş və nəticələr çıxarılmışdır.

Açar sözlər: DL optimallaşdırma alqoritmləri, reqressiya təhlili problemlərində səmərəliliyin qiymətləndirilməsi, təsvirlərin tanınması

1. Introduction

Deep learning has found wide applications in many areas of modern society, including computer vision, language analysis, financial services, medicine, and more.

It plays an important role in modern society, expanding the possibilities of computer processing of data and automation of processes, allowing to obtain new knowledge from a large amount of data, improve the accuracy of forecasting and solve complex problems that were previously considered unattainable. Thanks to its capabilities, deep learning continues to develop and find new applications in various industries, contributing to technological progress and innovation.

In turn, optimization algorithms are an important component of deep learning and are used to improve the learning process of neural networks. In the context of deep learning, optimizers are responsible for tuning model parameters in order to minimize the loss function and achieve optimal model accuracy or efficiency. Stochastic gradient descent algorithm, Adam, AdaGrad, RMSprop and others can be distinguished among the popular ones in deep learning. Each of them has its own unique features and operating principles, and the choice of optimizer depends on the specific task and characteristics of training data.

The relevance of this work lies in improving the results of deep learning and the development of the industry as a whole. Comparative analysis of deep learning algorithms helps to understand how different optimization methods affect the quality and speed of learning models. This makes it possible to choose the best algorithm for a specific task, providing better results and efficient use of resources. Research in this area can contribute to improving the understanding of deep learning algorithms and implementing best practices in the development of future models.

Statement of the problem

The object of research is deep learning optimization algorithms: stochastic gradient descent (SGD), Adam, AdaGrad and RMSprop.

The subject of research is deep learning in forecasting tasks.

The purpose of the work is to study, define and compare the effectiveness of four deep learning optimization algorithms SGD, Adam, AdaGrad and RMSprop in different intelligence tasks.

This paper presents the task of comparative analysis of optimization methods. To do this, it is necessary to investigate the operation of optimization methods in the conditions of various forecasting problems and compare the results. A comparative analysis of optimization methods SGD, Adam, AdaGrad, RMSprop can be presented in the following stages:

1. Selection of tasks and data sets: Several prediction tasks are selected that include different types of data, such as structured data, text data, or images. An appropriate data set is selected for each task.

2. Implementation of models: Implementation of a deep learning model using optimization algorithms. It is important to ensure that the models are identical in architecture, except for the optimization method.

3. Model training: Model training using appropriate optimization methods. At this stage, important parameters such as learning rate, number of training epochs, and batch size need to be fixed.

4. Measuring metrics: Measuring performance metrics for each model, such as accuracy, loss, or root mean square error, on the test data set after each training epoch. Metrics are recorded for later comparison.

5. Analysis of results: Comparison of results for models using SGD, Adam, AdaGrad and RMSprop methods. Checking the rate of convergence of each method, observing the change of metrics during training and comparing their value at the end point of the training. A consideration of which methods work best for different types of data and forecasting tasks.

2. Description of data

The work uses 5 data sets downloaded using the tensorflow.keras.datasets library:

2.1. Boston Housing

The Boston Housing dataset is a dataset widely used in machine learning and statistics. It was first introduced by researchers at the US Census Bureau and the University of Chicago in 1978, and has since become the benchmark dataset for regression analysis and predictive modeling.

The dataset contains information on house prices in the suburbs of Boston, Massachusetts. It consists of 506 samples, each representing a different suburb. For each suburb, there are 13 different features or attributes that describe different aspects of the area. These characteristics

are used to predict the median value of owner-occupied homes in thousands of dollars (the target variable).

The 13 functions included in the data set are as follows [1]:

CRIM: Crime rate per capita by city.

ZN: Proportion of residential land allocated to lots over 25,000 square feet.

INDUS: Proportion of non-retail business acres per city.

CHAS: Charles River dummy variable (1 if the suburb borders the river; 0 otherwise).

NOX: concentration of nitrogen oxides (parts per 10 million).

RM: Average number of rooms per dwelling.

AGE: Proportion of owner-occupied apartments built before 1940.

DIS: weighted distances to five Boston employment centers.

RAD: Radial Access Index.

TAX: Full property tax rate for \$10,000.

PTRATIO: Pupil/Teacher Ratio by City.

B: $1000 \cdot (B_k - 0.63)^2$, where B_k is the share of black people in cities.

LSTAT: Percentage of lower status population.

Each sample in the data set represents a suburb, and the features reflect different characteristics of the suburb that may affect house prices. A dummy variable, the mean of owner-occupied homes, is provided for each suburb.

Boston Housing is often used to explore regression techniques, evaluate the performance of algorithms, and study the relationship between housing prices and given attributes. It has been a valuable resource for machine learning researchers and practitioners in developing and testing house price forecasting models and related analysis

2.2. The "IMDb Movie Reviews" dataset is a popular dataset often used in natural language processing and sentiment analysis.

The dataset contains a large number of movie reviews collected from the IMDb website, a popular online database of movies, TV shows, etc. (Fig. 1.1). The reviews in this dataset cover a wide range of films, genres, and sentiments expressed by reviewers. Each review in the dataset is labeled with one of two sentiments: positive or negative, indicating whether the reviewer had a positive or negative opinion about the movie. This binary classification setting makes it suitable for training and

evaluating models that aim to classify text into positive or negative sentiment categories.

Importantly, this dataset primarily focuses on binary sentiment classification, and reviews may not reflect the full diversity of movie genres, languages, or cultural backgrounds. Therefore, when working with it, it is important to keep these limitations in mind and consider additional data sources or metrics to gain a full understanding of the effectiveness of sentiment analysis.

2.3. CIFAR-10

The "CIFAR-10" dataset is a widely used dataset in the field of computer vision and machine learning. It consists of a set of labeled images specially designed for object recognition tasks. The name CIFAR-10 stands for "Canadian Institute for Advanced Research 10" because it was created by researchers from the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research.

This dataset contains a total of 60,000 color images, each with a resolution of 32x32 pixels. These images are divided into ten different classes, with each class representing a specific category of objects (Fig. 1.2). The classes in the CIFAR-10 dataset are as follows:

- 1) airplane;
- 2) a car;
- 3) a bird;
- 4) a cat;
- 5) deer;
- 6) a dog;
- 7) frog;
- 8) horse;
- 9) a boat;
- 10) truck.

Figure 1.2 – Sample images of the "CIFAR-10" data set by categories [3]

The data set is divided into two subsets: the training set and the test set. The training set consists of 50,000 images, while the test set contains 10,000 images. This separation allows researchers and practitioners to train their models on large amounts of data and then evaluate their performance on unknown examples.

CIFAR-10 creates a challenging task for image classification algorithms due to its relatively low resolution and presence of different object categories. It has been widely used as a benchmark dataset to evaluate the performance of various computer vision models and algorithms, including convolutional neural networks. Researchers and practitioners use it to develop and test approaches to object recognition, feature extraction, and image classification.

2.4. MNIST

The MNIST (Modified NIST) database is a large database of handwritten digits commonly used to train various image processing systems. It was created by "remixing" samples from the original NIST data sets. The developers believed that because the NIST training dataset was taken from US Census Bureau employees and the test dataset was taken from US high school students, it was not suitable for machine learning experiments. In addition, the black and white images from NIST were

normalized to fit within a 28x28 pixel bounding box and smoothed to introduce gray levels [4].

The MNIST dataset consists of a set of handwritten digits commonly used to train and evaluate image classification algorithms (Fig. 1.3). It was created to provide a standardized benchmark for comparing different machine learning models for the handwritten digit recognition task.

Figure 1.3 – Sample images from the dataset «MNIST» [5]

MNIST contains 60,000 training images and 10,000 test images. Half of the training set and half of the test set were taken from the NIST training dataset, while the other halves were taken from the test set. This separation allows researchers and practitioners to train their models on large amounts of data and then evaluate their performance on unknown examples. Each image in this dataset represents a single digit from 0 to 9. The goal is to develop a machine learning model that can accurately classify these images by their corresponding digits. Among the data are labels for each image indicating the actual number it represents. These labels are used during training to guide the training of the model and during evaluation to evaluate its accuracy.

The MNIST dataset has been widely used for the development and evaluation of various machine learning algorithms, particularly in the fields of image classification and deep learning. Many popular models and architectures, such as convolutional neural networks, have been trained and tested on this dataset. The simplicity and standardization of the MNIST dataset make it an ideal starting point for learning and experimenting with image classification tasks.

2.5. Reuters

The Reuters dataset is a widely used dataset in the field of natural language processing and text classification. It was specifically designed for text categorization tasks and was created by collecting news articles from Reuters news agency. Its popularity is explained by its diversity and real nature, which allows for a comprehensive assessment of the capabilities of models in processing complex news articles and topics.

The dataset contains a large number of news articles, each article is a document. The training set has 7769 documents, while the test set has 3019 documents [6]. These articles cover a variety of topics, including business, politics, sports, technology, and more.

One feature of the dataset is that it supports classification by multiple labels. This means that a news article can be assigned to several categories at the same time, allowing more detailed and complex topics to be assigned. This flexibility reflects a real-world scenario where news articles may cover multiple topics or have overlapping topics

3. Optimization Algorithms in Deep learning

Optimizer algorithms are an optimization method that helps improve the performance of a deep learning model. These optimization algorithms adjust neural network attributes such as weights and learning rate. Thus, they help reduce overall losses and improve accuracy. The problem of choosing the right weights for a model is a difficult task, since a deep learning model usually consists of millions of parameters. This makes it necessary to choose the appropriate optimization algorithm for your application.

The main optimizers in deep learning:

1. Gradient Descent: A basic optimizer used to update model parameters in the direction opposite to the gradient of the loss function. Its goal is to minimize the value of the loss function by finding a local or global minimum.

2. Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD): Uses only one random data sample in each iteration to update model parameters. This reduces the computational cost, but may slow down the speed of convergence.

3. Variations of SGD: These are variations of stochastic gradient descent used to improve convergence and avoid getting stuck in local minima. These include Momentum, Nesterov Accelerated Gradient, AdaGrad, RMSprop and Adam.

4. Adaptive methods: Optimizers that adaptively adjust the learning rate for each parameter based on the gradient history. They allow faster learning for parameters that have smaller gradients and slower learning for parameters with large gradients. Examples of such optimizers include AdaGrad, RMSprop, Adam.

5. Regularization: Some optimizers have built-in regularization techniques, such as L1 or L2 regularization, to control model retraining. This helps reduce parameter values and improve the overall generalization ability of the model.

The use of a particular optimizer depends on the specific task, network architecture, and available computing resources. Choosing the right optimizer can be critical to successfully training a model and achieving high performance.

3.1. Stochastic Gradient Descent optimization method

The Stochastic Gradient Descent Method (SGD) is an optimization algorithm used to train deep learning models. This method is based on gradient descent, which is used to find the local minimum of the loss function.

Let us have a set of training data with labels (x, y) , where x is the input data and y is the corresponding labels or target values. The task is to find model parameters that best approximate the relationship between x and y . For this, we use the loss function L , which measures the difference between the predicted values of the model and the true values.

The goal of SGD is to minimize the loss function L by updating the model parameters at each training step. The parameters are updated by performing an iterative process in which the gradient of the loss function is calculated in relation to the model parameters and the gradient descent step is performed.

The SGD algorithm for optimizing deep learning models can be described by the following steps [7]:

Initialize the model parameters θ .

Initialize the learning rate α .

Repeat until the stop criterion is reached:

Choose a random subset of training data (x,y) .

Calculate the predicted value of the model $f(x;\theta)$.

Calculate the gradient of the loss function $\nabla L(\theta;x,y)$ in relation to the model parameters.

Update model parameters: $\theta \leftarrow \theta - \alpha \cdot \nabla L(\theta;x,y)$.

Return the optimal values of model parameters θ .

SGD is a simple and fast optimization algorithm, but it can have problems with the speed of convergence and can suffer from large variability when the data is noisy or unbalanced. Therefore, there are modifications of SGD, such as Adam, AdaGrad, RMSprop, which are designed to improve its convergence and stability

AdaGrad optimization method

AdaGrad is a family of algorithms for stochastic optimization. Algorithms belonging to this family are similar to second-order stochastic gradient descent with a Hessian approximation of the optimized function. The name AdaGrad comes from Adaptive Gradient. It intuitively adapts the learning rate for each feature depending on the assumed geometry of the problem; in particular, it tends to assign higher learning rates to infrequent features, ensuring that parameter updates rely less on frequency and more on relevance. The algorithm itself can be written as follows [8]:

Initialize the learning rate α , usually a small value (for example, 0.01).

Initialize the time counter $t=0$.

Initialize the sum of squares of gradients G_0 to zero.

At each iteration t until the stopping criterion is reached:

Calculate the g_t gradient of the model based on the current batch of data

Increase the time counter: $t \leftarrow t+1$.

Update the sum of the squares of the gradients: $G_t \leftarrow G_{(t-1)} + g_t \odot g_t$.

Update model parameters: $\theta_t \leftarrow \theta_{(t-1)} - \alpha / (\sqrt{G_t} + \epsilon) \odot g_t$, where ϵ is a very small constant to prevent division by zero.

Return the optimal values of model parameters θ .

The basis of the AdaGrad method is the idea that the learning rate is adaptively adjusted for each parameter depending on the history of the gradients. The larger the previous gradients, the lower the learning rate for a given parameter, which avoids overflow and excessive parameter changes. Conversely, parameters that have low gradients will have a higher learning rate, leading to faster learning and convergence for those parameters

RMSprop optimization method

RMSprop (Root Mean Square Propagation) is an adaptive optimization algorithm used to tune the parameters of deep learning models. This method is a modification of the classic gradient descent, which allows more efficient movement towards the optimum by adapting the learning rate for each parameter separately.

The basic idea behind RMSprop is to give more weight to the most recent gradients, decreasing the learning rate value for parameters that have large gradients and increasing the learning rate for parameters with small gradients. This allows the learning rate to be adapted for each parameter depending on its contribution to the overall loss function.

The algorithm of the RMSprop optimization method has the following form [9]:

Initialize the model parameters θ .

Initialize the learning rate α .

Initialize the damping parameter β (usually close to 0.9).

Initialize the variable $r=0$, which will store the current accumulated squared gradients.

Repeat until the stop criterion is reached:

Choose a random subset of training data (x,y) .

Calculate the predicted value of the model $f(x; \theta)$.

Calculate the gradient of the loss function $\nabla L(\theta; x,y)$ in relation to the model parameters.

Update the accumulated gradient squares: $r \leftarrow \beta \cdot r + (1 - \beta) \cdot (\nabla L(\theta; x,y))^2$.

Update model parameters: $\theta = \theta - \alpha / \sqrt{r + \epsilon} \cdot \nabla L(\theta; x,y)$, where ϵ is a very small number for stability of calculations.

Return the optimal values of model parameters θ .

In step 5, the accumulated squared gradients are used to account for the history of the gradients. Applying the root mean square to r allows us to

normalize the values of the gradients by their standard deviations. This helps to adjust the learning rate for each parameter individually, decreasing the rate value for parameters with large gradients and increasing it for parameters with small gradients.

Thus, the RMSprop algorithm allows you to reduce the value of the learning rate for parameters that have large gradients, thereby improving the convergence rate of the model optimization.

Adam (Adaptive Moment Estimation)

Adam (Adaptive Moment Estimation) is one of the popular optimization methods for training neural networks. It combines two approaches: adaptive learning rate and optimization moment.:

An adaptive gradient algorithm (AdaGrad) that supports the learning rate of each parameter, which improves performance in problems with smooth gradients (such as natural language and computer vision problems).

Root Mean Square Propagation (RMSprop), which also supports the learning rate of each parameter, adapted based on the average recent value of the gradients for the weight (eg, how fast it is changing). This means that the algorithm copes well with online and non-stationary problems (such as noise).

Adam implements the advantages of both AdaGrad and RMSProp [10].

The method calculates the exponentially weighted mean square of the gradients (the first moment) and the exponentially weighted mean square of the previous gradients (the second moment). These mean squares are used to adaptively adjust the learning rate for each parameter.

Adam also uses an optimization moment that helps account for gradient inertia when updating model parameters. This allows to speed up the optimization and reduce the probability of getting stuck in local minima. The method has parameters worth tuning, such as learning rate, exponential smoothing factors, and initial moment values. Setting these parameters can affect the optimization process and the speed of convergence.

In general, the Adam optimization method is an effective algorithm for training neural networks because it combines adaptive learning rate and optimization moment to efficiently search for optimal model parameter values.

The algorithm of the method can be described in the following steps [11]:

Initialize the learning rate α (usually a small value, e.g. 0.001).

Initialize the exponential smoothing coefficients β_1 and β_2 in the interval $[0,1)$ (usually $\beta_1=0.9, \beta_2=0.999$).

Initialize the time counter $t=0$.

Initialize the first moments of the gradients $m_0=0$ and the second moments of the gradients $v_0=0$.

At each iteration t :

Calculate the g_t gradient of the model based on the current batch of data.

Increase the time counter: $t \leftarrow t+1$.

Update the first and second moments of the gradients:

$$m_t \leftarrow \beta_1 \cdot m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) \cdot g_t;$$

$$v_t \leftarrow \beta_2 \cdot v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) \cdot g_t^2.$$

Виправити зміщення моментів:

$$\hat{m}_t \leftarrow m_t / (1 - \beta_1^t);$$

$$\hat{v}_t \leftarrow v_t / (1 - \beta_2^t).$$

Оновити параметри моделі:

$$\theta_t \leftarrow \theta_{t+1} - \alpha \cdot \frac{\hat{m}_t}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_t + \epsilon}},$$

4. Metrics

Metrics in deep learning are numerical scores used to measure the quality of deep learning models. The role of metrics in deep learning is to provide objective and quantitative evaluation of the model. They allow you to compare different models or different model hyperparameters and help you make decisions about improving the model.

There are many different kinds of metrics in deep learning, and the choice of specific metrics depends on the problem, the type of data, and the features of the model. The main types of metrics include:

1. Classification metrics: Used to evaluate the quality of models in classification tasks where classes need to be predicted. Examples include accuracy, recall, precision, F1-score, confusion matrix, etc.

2. Regression metrics: Used to evaluate models in regression problems where numerical values are to be predicted. For example, mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE), coefficient of determination (R-squared, or R2 Score), etc.

3. Clustering metrics: Used in non-learning tasks where the model clusters similar objects or examples into groups or clusters based on similarity. Examples of clustering metrics include Adjusted Rand Index, Normalized Mutual Information, silhouette coefficient, etc.

4. Generative model metrics: Used to evaluate generative learning models such as generative convolutional networks (GANs). Examples: inception score, Fréchet inception distance, user rating, etc.

Let's consider some of them in more detail.

The discrepancy matrix is an important metric for evaluating model classification results in machine learning tasks. It allows you to visualize and quantify the interaction between predicted and actual classes. The matrix is a two-dimensional square array, where the rows correspond to the true classes and the columns to the predicted classes. Each element of the discrepancy matrix shows the number of examples that were correctly or incorrectly classified.

The main elements of the matrix of inconsistencies:

1. True Positive (TP): Number of examples that are correctly classified as positive.

2. True Negative (TN): Number of examples correctly classified as negative.

3. False Positive (FP): Number of examples incorrectly classified as positive.

4. False Negative (FN): Number of examples incorrectly classified as negative.

Inconsistencies An example of a 2x2 (discrepancy) inconsistencies matrix is shown in Figure 4.1:

		Real state	
		Positive state	Negative state
Predicted state	Positive predicted state	Really positive	False positive Error of the I kind
	Negative predicted state	False negative Error of the II kind	Really negative

Figure 4.1 – Matrix of inconsistencies [12]

The matrix of inconsistencies allows you to measure the effectiveness of the model by revealing the number of correct and incorrect classifications. Based on this matrix, it is possible to calculate various metrics, such as accuracy, completeness (recall), precision, F1-measure (F1-score) and others, which help to evaluate the quality of model classification.

Accuracy is one of the most common and simple metrics in evaluating classification models in machine learning. It measures the ratio of the number of correctly classified examples to the total number of examples in the data set.

Accuracy allows you to evaluate the overall effectiveness of the classification model, taking into account both correctly defined positive and negative classes. This metric is particularly useful when the classes in the data set are of roughly equal importance or evenly distributed, but at the same time can be misleading when there is an unbalanced data set where one class dominates the other.

The accuracy is calculated according to the formula [13]:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+F}$$

Recall, (or sensitivity) also known as true positive rate (TPR), measures the percentage of correctly identified positive examples (true positives) out of the total number of valid positive examples in the data set.

Recall is calculated according to the formula [14]:

$$\text{Recall} = TP / (TP + FN)$$

Recall (Completeness) measures how effectively the model identifies positive classes. It indicates the ability of the model to detect all valid positive examples without errors. A high recovery value means that the model identifies positive examples well and minimizes the number of false negatives.

Recall (Completeness) is especially important in tasks where it is important to identify all positive examples, even at the risk of obtaining some false positives. For example, in medical diagnosis, disease detection is critical, so completeness may be more important than accuracy.

Precision is a metric in the evaluation of classification models and measures the percentage of correctly identified positive examples (true positives) out of the total number of examples that the model identified as positive.

$$\text{Precision} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FP})$$

F1-measure (F1-score) is a harmonic mean between precision and completeness (recall). It is used to assess the balance between model accuracy and completeness.

F1-measure is calculated according to the formula [15]:

$F1 = (2 \cdot p \cdot r) / (p + r)$, where p is the accuracy of the model, r is the completeness of the model.

5. Measurement of metrics

At this stage, we collect the calculated metrics as a result of model training. The metrics used depend on the prediction task for which we performed deep learning. MAE, MSE, R2 score and Explained Variance Score metrics were used in the regression problem.

Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1-score metrics were measured for classification tasks. In order to effectively compare the model with different optimizers, the values of losses and metrics calculated on the training and validation data were fixed at the model training stage. Validation data is used to evaluate the performance of the model during training and allows comparison of different optimization methods in the context of how they affect model losses and metrics. On the other hand, after training the model, it is best to make comparisons on independent test data that did not participate in the training and validation models. Using such data allows you to evaluate the model's real-world performance on new examples that the model has not seen before, helping to avoid overtraining and determining how well the model generalizes to new data. All measurements were tabulated (Tabl. 5.1-5.5) for each task. For the regression problem: Training data size: (404, 13) Test data size: (102, 13) To train the model, the training data was divided as follows: 85% training data, 15% validation data.

Table 5.1 – Measurement metrics for the regression problem with the Boston Housing

Optimizati on Algorithms	Loss	MAE	MSE	R2 score	Explained Variance	Time of execution	Number of epochs
SGD	10.8916	2.3318	10.8916	0.7969	0.7969	12.86 sec	150

Optimizati on Algorithms	Loss	MAE	MSE	R2 score	Explained Variance	Time of execution	Number of epochs
Adam	18.5565	2.6977	18.5565	0.5178	0.5178	8.88 sec	
AdaGrad	69.1414	6.8074	69.1414	0.0230	0.0230	9.53 sec	
RMSprop	15.3131	2.5649M	15.3131	0.6317	0.6317	9.15 sec	

For the classification problem with the "IMDB Movie Reviews" data set:

Size of training data: (25000, 60)

Test data size: (25000, 60)

To train the model, the training data was divided as follows: 80% training data, 20% validation data.

Table 5.2 – Metrics estimation for classification problem with data set «IMDB Movie Reviews»

Optimizati on Algorithms	Loss	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Time of execution	Number of epochs
SGD	0.6908	0.5650	0.6029	0.3809	0.4573	401.59 sec	10
Adam	1.0796	0.7867	0.8006	0.7637	0.7764	530.05 sec	
AdaGrad	0.6924	0.5419	0.5303	0.7339	0.6091	354.91 sec	
RMSprop	0.6782	0.7949	0.8506	0.7154	0.7714	424.68 sec	

For the problem of image classification with the "CIFAR-10" data set:

Size of training data: (50000, 32, 32, 3)

Test data size: (10000, 32, 32, 3)

To train the model, the training data was divided as follows: 80% training data, 20% validation data.

Table 5.3 – Measurement metrics for the classification problem with the “CIFAR-10»

Optimizati on Algorithms	Loss	Accurac y	Precisio n	Recal l	F1 score	Time of executio n	Numbe r of epochs
SGD	1.0233	0.6405	0.7734	0.5069	0.6094	398.60 sec	10
Adam	1.0614	0.6622	0.7203	0.6089	0.6588	461.71 sec	
AdaGrad	1.6220	0.4353	0.7077	0.1213	0.2034	465.36 sec	
RMSprop	1.0189	0.6962	0.7426	0.6634	0.6999	483.40 sec	

For the problem of image classification with the "MNIST" data set:
 Size of training data: (60000, 28, 28), Test data size: (10000, 28,

28)

To train the model, the training data was divided as follows: 80% training data, 20% validation

Table 5.4 – Measurement metrics for the classification problem with the “MNIST” dataset

Optimizati on Algorithms	Loss	Accurac y	Precisio n	Recal l	F1 score	Time of executio n	Numbe r of epochs
SGD	0.1201	0.9642	0.9717	0.9582	0.9648	111.67 sec	25
Adam	0.1159	0.9777	0.9783	0.9777	0.9780	135.93 sec	
AdaGrad	0.2760	0.9255	0.9501	0.9000	0.9236	126.16 sec	
RMSprop	0.1122	0.9795	0.9800	0.9793	0.9797	123.90 sec	

For the classification problem with the Reuters data set:

Size of training data: (8982, 1000) Test data size: (2246, 1000)

To train the model, the training data was divided as follows: 80% training data, 20% validation

Table 5.5 – Measurement metrics for the classification problem with the Reuters dataset

Optimization Algorithms	Loss	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Time of execution
SGD	1.1666	0.7324	0.8903	0.6362	0.7353	43.70 sec
Adam	1.3309	0.7858	0.8161	0.7685	0.7899	72.99 sec
AdaGrad	1.5598	0.6456	0.9058	0.4969	0.6348	53.41 sec
RMSprop	2.2609	0.7778	0.8163	0.7480	0.7787	ec

6. Analysis of experimental investigations

Analyzing the results of solving five forecasting problems using deep learning using optimization algorithms, the following observations can be made:

6.1. Regression problem:

1. The SGD algorithm showed the best results with the lowest value of losses and the best value of all metrics, but the training time turned out to be the largest.

2. Adam and RMSprop also performed well, but with higher losses and worse R2 Score and Explained Variance as compared to SGD.

3. AdaGrad performs worst with higher loss and low R2 Score and Explained Variance values.

6.2. Classification problem with the "IMDb Movie Reviews" data set:

1. Adam and RMSprop gave the best results. RMSprop has the best loss, precision and accuracy values, while Adam has the best completeness and F1 measures. However, Adam has the worst loss and execution time.

2. AdaGrad showed acceptable, but still lower results. Also, it turned out to be the fastest.

3. SGD showed the worst completeness and F1-measure, but slightly better than AdaGrad in precision and accuracy.

6.3. Classification problem with the "CIFAR10" data set:

1. Again, the best results were shown by Adam and RMSprop, only slightly different from each other.

2. SGD performed worse compared to the previous two, but was still good enough. Moreover, it turned out to be the fastest in this task.

3. AdaGrad showed the worst values for all metrics and losses except execution time.

6.4. Classification problem with the "MNIST" data set:

1. RMSprop this time showed the best loss and metrics results.
2. Adam has worse results compared to RMSprop, but is still quite close to it.
3. SGD performed worse with higher loss and lower values of precision, accuracy, completeness and F1-measure. It also has the lowest execution time. On the other hand, Adam worked the longest.
4. AdaGrad again performed worst with higher loss and lower values of precision, accuracy, completeness and F1-measure compared to Adam and SGD, but still had an acceptable result. It is also visible from the graphs that during the training of the model, the accuracy gradually decreases.

6.5. Classification problem with the "Reuters" data set:

1. Adam showed the best results in accuracy, completeness and F1 measure, but was the worst in Precision.
2. SGD showed acceptable results with comparatively lower precision, completeness and F1-measures, but achieved a good value of accuracy and has the least loss and execution time.
3. Adagrad performed worse with higher loss and lower accuracy, completeness and F1-measure values, but this time it was the best in accuracy. He was also quite fast.
4. RMSprop had better accuracy than Adam and almost the same accuracies, completeness and F1 measure, but at the same time has the worst loss and execution time.
5. According to the graphs, the losses for the Adam and RMSprop methods on the validation data set gradually increase, which is different from the corresponding ones on the training set. This may indicate retraining of these models.

Final conclusions.

1. RMSprop turned out to be the most effective optimization algorithm in most of the considered problems. It achieved the highest prediction accuracy and the best values of metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 Score.
2. SGD also performed well in some tasks, especially in the regression task, where it had the lowest loss and the highest R2 Score and Explained Variance.

3. Adam also showed generally excellent results and although sometimes he did not reach the highest values of the metrics, he was still close to it.

4. AdaGrad appeared to be less efficient compared to the others, showing lower values of prediction accuracy and losses. This was especially noticeable in classification tasks, where the method often showed the worst values of the metrics.

5. SGD and AdaGrad generally perform faster than Adam and RMSprop, especially on large tasks with large data sizes.

Bibliography (Transliterated)

[1] Boston Housing. Kaggle. [Electronic resource] – URL:<https://www.kaggle.com/c/boston-housing> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[2] IMDb Movie Reviews. PapersWithCode. [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://paperswithcode.com/dataset/imdb-movie-reviews> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[3] Alex Krizhevsky. The CIFAR-10 dataset. [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/cifar.html> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[4] MNIST database. Wikipedia. [Electronic resource] – URL:https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MNIST_database (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[5] Tim Hargreaves. Is it Time to Ditch the MNIST Dataset?. Ttested. [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://www.ttested.com/ditch-mnist/> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[6] Martin Thoma. The Reuters Dataset. 2017. [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://martin-thoma.com/nlp-reuters/> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[7] Ian Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio, Aaron Courville. Deep Learning (Adaptive Computation and Machine Learning series). Cambridge, Massachusetts, London, England: MIT Press, 2016.

[8] Daniel Villarraga. AdaGrad. Cornell University Computational Optimization Open Textbook. 2021. [Electronic resource] – URL:<https://optimization.cbe.cornell.edu/index.php?title=AdaGrad> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[9] Tieleman, T. and Hinton, G. Lecture 6.5 «RMSprop: Divide the Gradient by a Running Average of Its Recent Magnitude». COURSERA: Neural Networks for Machine Learning, 2012.

[10] Jason Brownlee. Gentle Introduction to the Adam Optimization Algorithm for Deep Learning. Machine Learning Mastery. July 3, 2017 (upd. January 13, 2021). [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://machinelearningmastery.com/adam-optimization-algorithm-for-deep-learning/> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[11] Diederik P. Kingma, Jimmy Ba, Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization. International Conference on Learning Representations, 2015. [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.6980> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[12] Матриця невідповідностей. Wikipedia. [Electronic resource] – URL: https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Матриця_невідповідностей (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[13] Accuracy and precision. Wikipedia. [Electronic resource] – URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Accuracy_and_precision (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[14] Precision and recall. Wikipedia. [Electronic resource] – URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Precision_and_recall (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[15] F-score. Wikipedia. [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/F-score> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[16] Shervin Minaee. Popular Machine Learning Metrics. Part 1: Classification & Regression Evaluation Metrics. Towards Data Science: October 28, 2019. [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://towardsdatascience.com/20-popular-machine-learning-metrics-part-1-classification-regression-evaluation-metrics-1ca3e282a2ce> (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[17] Коефіцієнт детермінації. Wikipedia. [Electronic resource] – URL: https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Коефіцієнт_детермінації (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[18] Tensorflow Keras documentation. [Electronic resource] – URL: https://www.tensorflow.org/api_docs/python/tf/keras (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[19] Ayush Gupta. A Comprehensive Guide on Optimizers in Deep Learning. Analytics Vidhya: October 7, 2021 (upd. May 18, 2023). [Electronic resource] – URL: https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2021/10/a-comprehensive-guide-on-deep-learning-optimizers/#What_Are_Optimizers_in_Deep_Learning? (date of access: 06/05/2024)

[20] Optimization Algorithms. Dive Into Deep Learning. [Electronic resource] – URL: https://d2l.ai/chapter_optimization/ (date of access: 06/05/2024)

Список литературы (перевод)

[1] Жилье Бостона. Кэгл. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/c/boston-housing> (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[2] Обзоры фильмов на IMDb. Документы с кодом. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://paperswithcode.com/dataset/imdb-movie-reviews> (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[3] Алекс Крижевский. Набор данных CIFAR-10. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/cifar.html> (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[4] База данных MNIST. Википедия. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MNIST_database (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[5] Тим Харгривз. Не пора ли отказаться от набора данных MNIST? Проверено. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://www.ttested.com/ditch-mnist/> (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[6] Мартин Тома. Набор данных Рейтер. 2017. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://martin-thoma.com/nlp-reuters/> (дата обращения: 05.06.2024).

[7] Ян Гудфеллоу, Йошуа Бенджио, Аарон Курвиль. Глубокое обучение (серия «Адаптивные вычисления и машинное обучение»). Кембридж, Массачусетс, Лондон, Англия: MIT Press, 2016.

[8] Даниэль Вильяррага. АдаГрад. Открытый учебник Корнельского университета по вычислительной оптимизации. 2021. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://optimization.cbe.cornell.edu/index.php?title=AdaGrad> (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[9] Тилеман Т. и Хинтон Г. Лекция 6.5 «RMSprop: разделите градиент на скользящее среднее его недавней величины». COURSERA: Нейронные сети для машинного обучения, 2012.

[10] Джейсон Браунли. Нежное введение в алгоритм оптимизации Адама для глубокого обучения. Мастерство машинного обучения. 3 июля 2017 г. (обновление от 13 января 2021 г.). [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://machinelearningmastery.com/adam-optimization-algorithm-for-deep-learning/> (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[11] Дидерик П. Кингма, Джимми Ба, Адам: метод стохастической оптимизации. Международная конференция по изучению представлений, 2015. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.6980> (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[12] Матрица невідповідностей. Википедія. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Матриця_невідповідностей (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[13] Точность и прецизионность. Википедія. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Accuracy_and_precision (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[14] Точность и отзыв. Википедія. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Precision_and_recall (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[15] F-оценка. Википедія. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/F-score> (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[16] Шервин Минаи. Популярные метрики машинного обучения. Часть 1: Метрики классификации и регрессионной оценки. На пути к науке о данных: 28 октября 2019 г. [Электронный ресурс] — URL: <https://towardsdatascience.com/20-popular-machine-learning-metrics-part-1-classification-regression-evaluation-metrics-1ca3e282a2ce> (дата публикации), доступ: 05.06.2024)

[17] Коэффициент детерминации. Википедія. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Коефіцієнт_детермінації (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[18] Документация Tensorflow Keras. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: https://www.tensorflow.org/api_docs/python/tf/keras (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[19] Аюш Гупта. Комплексное руководство по оптимизаторам в глубоком обучении. Аналитика Видгья: 7 октября 2021 г. (обновление от 18 мая 2023 г.). [Электронный ресурс] – URL: https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2021/10/a-comprehensive-guide-on-deep-learning-optimizers/#What_Are_Optimizers_in_Deep_Learning? (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

[20] Алгоритмы оптимизации. Погрузитесь в глубокое обучение. [Электронный ресурс] – URL: https://d2l.ai/chapter_optimization/ (дата обращения: 05.06.2024)

İstinadlar (tərcümə)

- [1] Boston Housing. Caggle. [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/c/boston-housing> (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)
- [2] IMDb-də film rəyləri. Kodlu sənədlər. [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://paperswithcode.com/dataset/imdb-movie-reviews> (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)
- [3] Aleks Krijevski. CIFAR-10 verilənlər toplusu. [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/cifar.html> (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)
- [4] MNIST verilənlər bazası. Vikipediya. [Elektron resurs] – URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MNIST_database (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)
- [5] Tim Hargreaves. MNIST məlumat dəstini ləğv etməyin vaxtıdır? Doğrulanıb. [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://www.ttested.com/ditch-mnist/> (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)
- [6] Martin Toma. Reuters məlumat toplusu. 2017. [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://martin-thoma.com/nlp-reuters/> (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024).
- [7] Ian Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio, Aaron Courville. Dərin Öyrənmə (Adaptiv Hesablama və Maşın Öyrənmə Seriyası). Cambridge, MA, London, İngiltərə: MIT Press, 2016.
- [8] Daniel Villarraga. AdaGrad. Cornell Universiteti Hesablama Optimizasiyası üzrə Açıq Dərslik. 2021. [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://optimization.cbe.cornell.edu/index.php?title=AdaGrad> (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)
- [9] Tieleman T. və Hinton G. Mühazirə 6.5 “RMSprop: qradiyenti onun son böyüklüyünün hərəkətli ortasına bölün.” COURSERA: Maşın öyrənməsi üçün neyron şəbəkələri, 2012.
- [10] Ceyson Braunli. Dərin öyrənmə üçün Adam optimallaşdırma alqoritminə incə giriş. Maşın öyrənmə ustalığı. 3 iyul 2017-ci il (13 yanvar 2021-ci il yeniləndi). [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://machinelearningmastery.com/adam-optimization-algorithm-for-deep-learning/> (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)
- [11] Diederik P. Kingma, Jimmy Ba, Adam: Stokastik optimallaşdırma metodu. Nümayəndəliklərin Tədqiqi üzrə Beynəlxalq Konfrans, 2015. [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.6980> (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)
- [12] Uyğunsuzluqlar matrisi. Vikipediya. [Elektron resurs] – URL: https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Matrix_of_irregularities (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)

[13] Dəqiqlik və dəqiqlik. Vikipediya. [Elektron resurs] – URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Accuracy_and_precision (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)

[14] Dəqiqlik və geri çağırma. Vikipediya. [Elektron resurs] – URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Precision_and_recall (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)

[15] F-balı. Vikipediya. [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/F-score> (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)

[16] Şervin Minai. Populyar maşın öyrənmə göstəriciləri. Hissə 1: Təsnifat və Reqrəssiya Metrikləri. Məlumat Elminə Doğru: 28 oktyabr 2019-cu il [Elektron resurs] – URL: <https://towardsdatascience.com/20-popular-machine-learning-metrics-part-1-classification-regression-evaluation-metrics-1ca3e282a2ce> (dərc tarixi: 06/05/2024)

[17] Determinasiya əmsalı. Vikipediya. [Elektron resurs] – URL: https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Əyləncə_əmsalı (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)

[18] Tensorflow Keras sənədləri. [Elektron resurs] – URL: https://www.tensorflow.org/api_docs/python/tf/keras (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)

[19] Ayuş Qupta. Dərin öyrənmədə optimallaşdırıcılar üçün hərtərəfli bələdçi. Vidya Analytics: 7 oktyabr 2021 (Yenilənib 18 may 2023). [Elektron resurs] – URL: https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2021/10/a-comprehensive-guide-on-deep-learning-optimizers/#Deep_Learning-də_Optimizatorlar_Nə_dir? (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)

[20] Optimallaşdırma alqoritmləri. Özünü dərin öyrənməyə qərq edin. [Elektron resurs] – URL: https://d2l.ai/chapter_optimization/ (giriş tarixi: 06/05/2024)

© G.I. Hamidov, 2024

Поступила в редакцию 24.05.2024

Принята к публикации 06.06.2024

Для цитирования:

G.I. Hamidov Investigations of deep learning algorithms in the problems of classification, forecasting, images processing and recognition // Инновационные научные исследования. 2024. № 6-1(43). С. 56-82. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>